

ENDOCRINE DISORDERS IN THE CONTEXT OF COVID-19

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Annotation. Most endocrine diseases are chronic, with up to 80% of cases occurring in patients with endocrinopathies, primarily diabetes mellitus and thyroid diseases, who receive regular outpatient care. For such people, an endocrinologist is most often also a general practitioner, so it is their responsibility to promptly explain to patients with diabetes, thyroid, pituitary and adrenal diseases, and endocrine tumors how to behave in the new conditions of the coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic. This infectious disease is most severe in people over 65 years of age with chronic diseases, especially endocrinopathies. This literature review summarizes the current information on the pathogenesis and course of COVID-19, including in the most vulnerable groups. The article provides up-to-date information on measures to prevent infection, the specifics of patient-doctor contact in conditions of self-isolation and quarantine measures, as well as what additional treatment measures are necessary in the development of COVID-19 in patients with the most severe endocrinopathies.

Keywords. COVID-19, SARS-CoV-2, endocrinopathy, diabetes.

Аннотация. Большинство заболеваний эндокринной системы имеют хроническое течение, до 80% случаев приходится на пациентов с эндокринопатией, первичным сахарным диабетом и щитовидной железой, получающих регулярную амбулаторную помощь. Для таких людей эндокринолог часто работает с врачом общей практики, поэтому именно на них ложится ответственность - оперативно объяснить моему пациенту сахарный диабет, заболевания щитовидной железы, гипофиза и надпочечников, опухоли эндокринной системы, а также новые состояния пандемии коронавируса (COVID-19). Тяжелее всего это инфекционное заболевание протекает у лиц старше 65 лет, имеющих хронические заболевания, особенно эндокринопатии. Данные обзора литературы суммируют имеющиеся на сегодняшний день сведения о патогенезе и течении COVID-19, в том числе в наиболее уязвимых группах. В статье представлена актуальная информация о профилактике заражения, особых условиях контакта «пациент-врач» и условиях самоизоляции и карантинных мероприятий, а также какие дополнительные медицинские мероприятия необходимы при развитии COVID-19 и у больных со стрессовой эндокринопатией.

Ключевые слова. COVID-19, SARS-CoV-2, эндокринопатия, сахарный диабет.

Izoh. Endokrin tizim kasalliklarining aksariyati surunkali bo'lib, 80% hollarda endokrinopatiya, birlamchi qandli diabet va qalqonsimon bez muntazam ravishda ambulator yordam ko'rsatadigan bemorlarda uchraydi. Bu odamlar uchun endokrinolog tez-tez umumiy amaliyot shifokori bilan ishlaydi, shuning uchun bemorga diabet, qalqonsimon bez, gipofiz va buyrak usti bezi kasalliklari, endokrin tizim o'smalari va koronavirus (COVID-19) pandemiyasining yangi shartlarini tezda tushuntirish nixning mas'uliyati hisoblanadi. Ushbu yuqumli kasallik surunkali kasalliklarga, ayniqsa endokrinopatiyaga ega bo'lgan 65 yoshdan oshgan odamlarda eng og'ir. Adabiyotlarni ko'rib chiqish ma'lumotlari COVID-19 patogenezi va rivojlanishi, shu jumladan eng zaif guruhlardagi mavjud dalillarni jamlaydi. Maqolada infektsiyaning oldini olish, bemor va shifokor bilan aloqa qilish uchun maxsus shartlar va

o'zini-o'zi izolyatsiya qilish va karantin choralari, shuningdek, COVID-19 rivojlanishi paytida qanday qo'shimcha tibbiy choralar zarurligi haqida dolzarb ma'lumotlar keltirilgan. stressli endokrinopatiya bilan og'riqan bemorlar.

Kalit so'zlar. COVID-19, SARS-CoV-2, endokrinopatiya, qandli diabet.

Relevance. Many endocrinopathies have a chronic course, and, at least in our country, up to 80% of people with chronic diseases who receive regular outpatient care are patients with endocrine disorders, primarily diabetes mellitus and thyroid diseases. For these people, an endocrinologist is most often a general practitioner, and therefore today, in our prosperous world so unaccustomed to epidemics, when only yesterday anti-vaccinationists gathered huge audiences that listened to them, and convincing people of the need for vaccination against influenza and other acute respiratory infections was extremely difficult, these specialists are responsible for promptly explaining to people with diabetes, diseases of the thyroid gland, pituitary gland and adrenal glands, tumors of the endocrine system, how to behave in the new conditions.

The purpose of this study. The aim of the review is to highlight the currently available information on the impact of SARS-CoV-2 infection on the thyroid gland (TG), the impact of thyroid pathology on the incidence and course of COVID-19, and the specifics of managing patients with various thyroid pathologies in the context of a new coronavirus infection.

Materials and methods of research. It is known that hypothalamic and pituitary tissues express ACE2 and may be potential targets of SARS-CoV-2 either directly or through an immune-mediated process, as has been demonstrated with other coronaviruses. Once in the nervous system, SARS-CoV-2 provokes oxidative stress, vasodilation, and thrombogenesis, which together can lead to hemorrhagic pituitary apoplexy.

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is considered a risk factor for worsening the course and development of severe forms of COVID-19 and mortality from it. The risk of developing severe forms, according to various sources, ranges from 16.2 to 9.2% and depends on age (elderly patients are at the highest risk), the presence of other diseases (patients with concomitant serious chronic diseases of the heart, lungs) and glycemic control (high risk with poor control, long history of DM, the presence of vascular complications). Chronic hyperglycemia causes dysfunction of the immune system and increases the risk of morbidity and mortality due to any infection, including COVID-19. The risk of death is increased by about 2 times. With DM, especially with vascular complications, the risk of renal and cardiac complications is increased.

Conclusion. The effect of SARS-CoV-2 on the endocrine system has not yet been sufficiently studied. Studies have shown that the virus can affect the gonads, thyroid gland, pituitary gland, adrenal glands and pancreas. There are known cases of manifestation of endocrine pathology after a previous infection with SARS-CoV-2: carbohydrate metabolism disorder, thyroid dysfunction and cases of subacute thyroiditis, adrenal dysfunction, changes in spermatogenesis in men. Given the very short history of COV-19, it is not yet possible to make final, well-founded conclusions about the consequences of the disease on the endocrine system; further long-term studies are needed to assess the effect of COV-19 on the endocrine glands.

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